

Is Reservation Policy of India an Impediment to Social Justice? A Critical Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The gross inadequate representation of the Schedule Caste, Schedule Tribes, and other backward classes in terms of education, employment and political participation due to the historic oppression and discriminated strata of society leads to the institutionalisation of reservation policy in India. Reservation policy of India encompasses a set of affirmative measures such as reserving access to seats in the basic and higher education, employment opportunities, legislative measures to preferential treatment to the most disadvantageous groups/marginalised sections of the society with respect to socio-economic development by promoting equality among the marginal groups so as to protect them from social injustice. Therefore, reservation policy has always been a watchword among the political sphere and also proved to be the most controversial public policy of the State due to its norms towards treating the different strata of the people. Therefore, the present study made an attempt to critically analyse the role of reservation policy in developing social justice and equality in the economy.

Keywords: Reservation Policy, Positive Discrimination, Underprivileged Groups, Social Justice, and Equality.

Prologue: “When more people aspire for backwardness rather than of forwardness, the country itself stagnates”

- Justice Ravindran

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Introduction

The gross inadequate representation of the Schedule Caste, Schedule Tribes, and other backward classes in terms of education, employment and political participation due to the historic oppression and discriminated strata of society leads to the institutionalisation of reservation policy in India. Reservation policy of India encompasses a set of affirmative measures such as reserving access to seats in the basic and higher education, employment opportunities, legislative measures to the socio-economic weaker sections of the society. It is also called as positive discrimination as it gives preferential treatment to the most disadvantageous groups/marginalised sections of the society with respect to socio economic development by promoting equality among the marginal groups so as to protect them from social injustice. Therefore, reservation policy has always been a watchword among the political sphere and also proved to be the most controversial public policy of the State due to its norms towards treating the different strata of the people.ⁱ

Reservation is the form of quota based on affirmative action institutionalised with a motto of providing special provisions to the marginalised groups (especially SCs & STs) who are subjected to historical oppression and discrimination in access to education, job opportunities and even political participation in order to uplift their life status. Historical oppression, caste-based discrimination, unequal treatment in access to and control over resources - decision making process, social exclusion, unemployment, income/wealth inequalities and so on were the major reasons behind the increasing demand for reservation policy in India.ⁱⁱ

Evolution of Reservation Policy – An Overview

- The idea of a caste-based reservation system was originally conceived by William Hunter and Jyotirao Phule in 1882.
- During the year 1902, Shahu, the Maharaja of the Princely State of Kolhapur, introduces reservation in favour of non-brahmin and backward classes in education.

- Mysore State initiated reservation for backward classes after a decade long social justice movement against the underprivileged groups (non-brahmin castes) in the year 1921
- In 1933 the Communal Award by British Government established the reservation system that exists today. It grants separate electorates in India for Muslims, Buddhists, Sikhs, Christians, Anglo-Indians, Europeans and Depressed Classes (then untouchables).
- Later, Poona Act was signed which reserved seats for depressed castes within Hindu Electorates.
- In 1942, Viceroy's Executive Council recommends 8.5 per cent reservation for Scheduled Castes in civil services.
- In 1950, the Constitution of India made a commitment for reservations for Scheduled Castes and Tribes.
- Followed by, in the year 1950, First amendment was made in the Constitution to legalise caste-based reservation.ⁱⁱⁱ
- In initial period, Reservations were exclusively available for SCs and STs after independence. Later, OBCs were included in the ambit of reservation in 1991 by the recommendations of the Mandal Commission.
- The Supreme Court, while sustaining the 27% quota for backward classes, overturned a government notification reserving 10% of government positions for economically backward classes among the higher castes in the Indra Sawhney Case of 1992.^{iv}
- The Constitutional (103rd Amendment) Act of 2019 has established a 10% reservation for the “economically disadvantaged” in government positions and educational institutions in the unreserved category. The Act adds language to Articles 15 and 16 of the Constitution allowing the government to grant reservations based on economic disadvantage.^v

Review of Literature

Rao (1992) examined the formulation of policy and arguments in favour and against in the context of merit principle. **Biswas (2018)**^{vi} discussed the implementations of reservations for SCs in education and government jobs from primary levels to higher education. The study stated that the preferential treatment on the basis of caste is the main problem dwells with the reservation policy of India as the benefits cannot be enjoyed as a whole but in partial or individual. **Singh and Ahmad (2019)** stated that reservation policy has brewed some controversies in the country which obstruct path of national growth and importance. The study also suggested uplifting the underprivileged groups with free education and other incentives which is helpful to make them capable to compete the true competition. **Das (2021)**^{vii} concluded that the reservation policy is perpetuating the notion of caste prevalence in society rather than eliminating it. **Upadhyay** claimed that reservation policy compromises the efficiency of the country as it fails to abolish the caste system and also excludes the merits of the backward classes who are supposed to be truly recognised. **Jangir (2013)**^{viii} concluded that the reservation policy was only for 10 years after the independence, for the upliftment of SCs and STs but till now it is continued and no one has taken any step to amend it or revise it or to change it.

Methodology of the Study

The study mainly based on qualitative analysis which deals with the critical examination of the reservation policy of India in creating social justice in the economy. The information was obtained from the secondary sources like books, journals, magazines, annual reports, thesis and websites.

Objectives of the Study

- To critically analyse the role of reservation policy in developing social justice and equality in the economy
- To suggest measures to augment the process of developing social justice and equality in the economy.

Reservation Policy of India – A Critical Analysis

India's reservation policy is considered to be the world's oldest of its kind. It is a form of quota based affirmative action which facilitates underprivileged/disadvantageous groups in education and employment opportunities who faced with prolonged injustice.^{ix} Its main motto is to resolve historic oppression, inequality and discrimination against SCs and STs and other backward classes and also meant to achieve the promise of equality enshrined in the Indian Constitution. Undoubtedly, it contracts the gap and differences between the upper and lower caste in socio-economic development indicators to a greater extent. The large number of SC/ST employees in Railways compared to others evident it. At the same time, it also hovers around many critics since from its inception. It has been criticised mainly of its stance towards the principle of meritocracy. It also been questioned whether it has been reinforcing caste-based differences in the society.^x Furthermore, it is also generally accepted that caste reservation policy is used as a tool for vote banking system to achieve narrow political goals.

Most of the studies on reservation policy of India insist the need for revisiting and evaluating the existing reservation policy^{xi} as it is considered to be a major threat to merit principle and of course attaining social justice in the economy. Meritocracy should not be ruined by lowering or relaxing the entry barriers rather, it should be boosted by providing financial assistance to the underprivileged. Due to political difficulties, there is a fear that once reservation is implemented, it will never be removed, even if there is proof of upliftment of backward classes. In Tamil Nadu, for example, forward castes were only able to acquire 3% of overall seats (and 9% in Open Competition) in professional schools at the undergraduate level, despite their population percentage of 13%. This is an obvious case of discrimination in the wrong direction. (Vaid, Lexpeeps, 2021).^{xii}

Reservation policy in India is given to Schedule Castes, Schedule Tribes, and backward classes at the percent of 15%, 7.5% and 27% respectively. Once introducing the reservation provision, it connected to vote bank for politics and later government and the Indian Parliament habitually spread this era with non-free and truthful revision. This may also harm the economic structure of the country (Kumar, 2022). Some argues that there is no need for reservation anymore as the majority of lower castes have stepped up the social ladder and are now on an equal status compared to the general population. Now a day reservation policy

becomes a mechanism of exclusion rather than of inclusion. The previously advantaged communities have becoming disadvantaged to a large extent due to the reservation conundrum (IAS Express, 2022). Most importantly reservation on the basis of caste and not on the basis of economic condition of the people sensed to be highly questionable and unjustifiable. Here are some of the questions put forward towards the reservation policy on its role on attaining social justice and equality in the economy.^{xiii}

- Why does it fail to develop the principle of meritocracy? Does it act against the principle of meritocracy.
- Many upper castes are still plagued by poverty and illiteracy. Equality and justice don't work for them - Why?
- Castes that should be actually benefitted are not being benefitted; instead, others are reaping the benefits of the reservation system again and again. Does the caste-based reservation policy reinforce the caste-based differences in the economy?
- This in turn, may cause social unrest. Does it promote social enmity?
- Does caste-based reservation policy affect the efficiency of the labour?
- Did reservation policy become a tool for vote bank politics?

Suggestions

From the overall analysis, the paper recommends a few suggestions/measures to improve the efficiency of reservation policy in delivering the benefits to the needs. Some of them are,

- Reservation policy can be developed on the basis of income/economic power in order to avoid caste reinforcement
- The principle of meritocracy should be made priority as it is the base for efficient administration and economic development of a country

- Effective monitoring mechanisms and strategies should be developed in order to address the truly deserved beneficiaries.
- Malpractices and loopholes should be eliminated so as to attain true social justice in terms socio-economy equality.
- Awareness on reservation policy should be generated among the population so as to reach the unreached.

Epilogue

Undeniably, the reservation policy of India has created a drastic change in reducing the disparities between the various strata of the society. It should be praised and celebrated as its achievement towards developing equity and equality in the economy is manifold. At the same time, it is equally important to revisit and reformulate its structure when it affects the society in terms of caste reinforcement, social unrest, and social enmity. It should be treated as a policy for developing social justice rather than consider it as a tool for vote bank politics. Effective strategies and mechanisms should be developed to curb out the malpractices in delivering the benefits to the socially and economically marginalised groups. Therefore, **Reforms on Reservation Policies is the need of the hour.**

Endnotes:

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ⁱⁱⁱ Gupta, **Reservation Policy under Indian Constitution**, 2018.

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^v Rai, S. *Social and Conceptual Background to the Policy of Reservation*. **Economic and Political Weekly**. 37(42),2002 pp. 4309-18

^{vi} Biswas, *Reservation Policy in India: Urge for Social Justice and Equality in Education and Government Service*, **International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews**, Vol. 5, Issue 3, 2018, pp. 80-84.

^{vii} Das, **An Analysis on the Evolution of Reservation Policy in India**

^{viii} Jangir, *Reservation Policy and Indian Constitution in India*, **American International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences**, ISSN (Online): 2328-3696, 2013, pp. 126-128

^{ix} Singa, *Caste Based Reservation in India – An Analysis*, **Social Work Chronicle**, Vol.1, Issue. I, 2012, pp. 117- 128